

Integrating foreign expertise: Human resource management of international knowledge workers in the headquarters of Chinese firms

Refereed Paper

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Abstract

Chinese firms increasingly recruit foreign executives and experts into their headquarters but little is known about this phenomenon. To close this gap we conduct interviews with international knowledge workers and their local peers. We find that the integration of foreign expertise is hampered by organizational mindsets that manifest in utilitarian polycentric approaches, bureaucratic personnel administration rather than talent management, and poor communication practices. Building on these triangulated data we develop theory on a limited ability of Chinese firms to pursue transnational strategies. Longitudinal analyses support our theory, even after accounting for exceptional cases. We draw on institutional theory to help explain how the observed phenomena may be shaped by the national context, and offer propositions, a model of influences, and suggestions for further research.

Keywords

HRM, headquarters, geocentric, transnational, global mindset, foreign expert, China